

TABLE A1
SEARCH TERMS

Concept	Keywords
Software visualization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • software visualization • software visualisation
Maintenance	maintenance, evolution, fault, defect, enhancement, adapt, change, debug, refactor, comprehension, test, analysis, cognitive

Fig. 1. Distribution of primary studies by type of publication

Fig. 2. Maintenance aspects improved by software visualization

Fig. 3. User roles identified in the use of software visualization

Fig. 4. Evaluation aspects assessed in primary studies

TABLE A2: Primary studies

ID	Year	Title	Authors
S01	2022	A New Generation of CLASS BLUEPRINT	Agouf NJ, Ducasse S, Etien A, Lanza M
S02	2021	A Scalable Log Differencing Visualisation Applied to COBOL Refactoring	Deknop C, Mens K, Bergel A, Fabry J, Zaytsev V
S03	2019	An Architecture-Tracking Approach to Evaluate a Modular and Extensible Flight Software for CubeSat Nanosatellites	Gonzalez CE, Rojas CJ, Bergel A, Diaz MA
S04	2021	Augmenting Code Review Experience Through Visualization	Balci F, Haliloglu DS, Sahin O, Tilki C, Yurtsever MA, Tuzun E
S05	2020	Boundary Value Exploration for Software Analysis	Dobslaw F, Neto FG, Feldt R
S06	2022	Bug-Fix Variants: Visualizing Unique Source Code Changes across GitHub Forks	Imamura D, Ishio T, Kula RG, Matsumoto K
S07	2019	Code house: VR code visualization tool	Hori A, Kawakami M, Ichii M
S08	2019	CodeArena: Inspecting and Improving Code Quality Metrics using Minecraft	Baars S, Meester S
S09	2022	CodePanorama: A language agnostic tool for visual code inspection	Etter M, Mehta F
S10	2024	CodeView: A Tool for Software Visualization in Development View	Jeffrey C, Nugroho AP, Rukmono SA, Widyani Y
S11	2021	Coding- Development Task Visualization for SW Code Comprehension	Kim T, Kim S, Ryu D
S12	2021	Codoc: Code-driven Architectural View Specification Framework in Python	Bang CW, Lungu M
S13	2024	Cognitive-Integrated Complexity Analysis: A Comprehensive Software Visualization Tool	Sampath KR, Silva DI
S14	2024	Collaborative Software Exploration with Multimedia Note Taking in Virtual Reality	Hoff A, Lungu M, Seidl C, Lanza M
S15	2019	Corpus vis-visualizing software metrics at scale	Slater J, Anslow C, Dietrich J, Merino L
S16	2022	Dbux-PDG: An Interactive Program Dependency Graph for Data Structures and Algorithms	Seifert D, Wan M, Hsu J, Yeh B
S17	2024	Debugging Activity Blueprint	Bourcier V, Bergel A, Etien A, Costiou S
S18	2023	DGT-AR: Visualizing Code Dependencies in AR	Freire-Pozo D, Cespedes-Arancibia K, Merino L, Fernandez-Blanco A, Neyem A, Alcocer JP
S19	2022	didiff: A Viewer for Comparing Changes in both Code and Execution Traces	Kanda T, Shimari K, Inoue K
S20	2024	Effectiveness of Performance Visualizations for Declarative Model Transformations	Groner R, Tichy M
S21	2020	Enhanced Visualization of Method Invocations by Extending Reverse-engineered Sequence Diagrams	Ghaleb TA, Aljasser K, Alturki MA
S22	2024	Enhancing HTML Structure Comprehension: Real-Time 3D/XR Visualization of the DOM	Moreno-Lumbreras D
S23	2024	Enhancing Software Security Visualization through Adaptive Level of Detail (LoD) Mechanisms: A City Metaphor-Based Approach	Devendra I, Wijesiriwardana C, Wimalaratne P
S24	2020	Evaluating a visual approach for understanding javascript source code	Dias M, Orellana D, Vidal S, Merino L, Bergel A
S25	2019	Exploring eye tracking data on source code via dual space analysis	Zhang L, Sun J, Peterson C, Sharif B, Yu H
S26	2024	Extending iTrace-Visualize to Support Token-based Heatmaps and Region of Interest Scarf Plots for Source Code	Behler JA, Villalobos G, Pangonis J, Sharif B, Maletic JI

ID	Year	Title	Authors
S27	2019	GoCity: Code City for Go	Brito R, Brito A, Brito G and Valente M
S28	2022	Heap Patterns for Memory Graph Visualization	Boockmann JH, Luttgen G
S29	2022	IDEvelopAR: A Programming Interface to enhance Code Understanding in Augmented Reality	Kreber L, Diehl S, Weil P
S30	2024	Immersive Software Archaeology: Collaborative Exploration and Note Taking in Virtual Reality	Hoff A, Lungu M, Seidl C, Lanza M
S31	2020	Interactive Role Stereotype-Based Visualization to Comprehend Software Architecture	Ho-Quang T, Bergel A, Nurwidyantoro A, Jolak R, Chaudron MR
S32	2024	Layered BubbleTea Software Architecture Visualisation	Rukmono SA, Chaudron MR, Jeffrey C
S33	2020	Moderate Detection and Removal of Omnipresent Modules in Software Clustering	Yano K, Matsuo A
S34	2023	MVVDroid: Android Malware Detection based on Multi-View Visualization	Guo J, Meng Z, Zhang Q, Xiong Y, Huang W
S35	2020	N-way Diff: Set-based Comparison of Software Variants	Duszynski S, Tenev VL, Becker M
S36	2020	PerfMinerArch - A Tool to Visualize and Analyze Performance Deviations	Silva LM, Silva LA, Kulesza U, Rodrigues DA, Pinto F
S37	2024	PIE: A Tool for Visualizing the Life Cycle of Design Patterns in Open Source Software Projects	Hussain K, Collins C, Bradbury JS
S38	2023	Preparing Software Re-Engineering via Freehand Sketches in Virtual Reality	Hoff A, Seidl C, Lungu M, Lanza M
S39	2020	REM: Visualizing the Ripple Effect on Dependencies Using Metrics of Health	Chen Z, German DM
S40	2022	Spike-A code editor plugin highlighting fine-grained changes	Escobar R, Alcocer JP, Turner H, Beck F, Bergel A
S41	2024	The Impact of a Live Refactoring Environment on Software Development	Fernandes S, Aguiar A, Restivo A
S42	2022	The Visual Debugger Tool	Krauter T, König H, Rutle A, Lamo Y
S43	2021	Towards Visual Analytics Dashboards for Provenance-driven Static Application Security Testing	Schreiber A, Sonnekalb T, Kurnatowski L
S44	2023	Traveler: Navigating Task Parallel Traces for Performance Analysis	Sakin SA, Bigelow A, Tohid R, Scully-Allison C, Scheidegger C, Brandt SR, Taylor C, Huck KA, Kaiser H, Isaacs KE
S45	2023	Understanding the NPM Dependencies Ecosystem of a Project Using Virtual Reality	Moreno-Lumbreras D, Gonzalez-Barahona JM, Lanza M
S46	2024	User-centered Software Visualization Design for Professional Developers	Heidrich D, Schreiber A
S47	2024	Using Interactive Animations to Analyze Fine-grained Software Evolution	Armenti C, Lanza M
S48	2023	Using Tool Support to Visualize and Interact with IEC 61499 Control Software	Bauer P, Sonnleithner L, Kutsia E, Rabiser R, Zoitl A
S49	2021	Vis-a-Vis: Visual Exploration of Visualization Source Code Evolution	Bolte F, Bruckner S
S50	2022	ViSRE: A Unified Visual Analysis Dashboard for Proactive Cloud Outage Management	Kayongo P, Hoffswell J, Saini S, Garg S, Koh E, Wang H, Jacobs T
S51	2020	Visual Breakpoint Debugging for Sum and Product Formulae	Moseler O, Wolz M, Diehl S
S52	2020	Visualization of Evolution of Component-Based Software Architectures in Virtual Reality	Heidmann EF, Kurnatowski L, Meinecke A, Schreiber A
S53	2019	Visualization of Variability Analysis of Control Software From Industrial Automation Systems	Bougouffa S, Vogel-Heuser B, Fischer J, Schaefer I, Li H
S54	2021	Visualizing Data in Software Cities	Ardigo S, Nagy C, Minelli R, Lanza M
S55	2021	Visualizing GitHub Issues	Fiechter A, Minelli R, Nagy C, Lanza M
S56	2022	Visualizing Memory Consumption with Vismep	Blanco AF, Bergel A, Alcocer JP, Cordova AQ
S57	2019	Visualizing sequences of debugging sessions using swarm debugging	Fontana EA, Petrillo F
S58	2023	Visually Analyzing Company-Wide Software Service Dependencies: An Industrial Case Study	Baltes S, Pfitzmann B, Kowark T, Treude C, Beck F
S59	2022	VizAPI: Visualizing Interactions between Java Libraries and Clients	Venkatanarayanan S, Dietrich J, Anslow C, Lam P
S60	2021	Voronoi Evolving Treemaps	Tua DP, Minelli R, Lanza M
S61	2024	Where Did My Memory Go? An Interactive Visualization Approach to Investigate Memory Consumption on Android Devices	Souza G, Matias P, Filho RM, Monteiro E, Barreto R, Freitas R

TABLE A3
SEARCH STRINGS

Data source	String
IEEE Xplore	("software visual*") AND ("maintenance" OR "evolution" OR "fault" OR "defect" OR "enhancement" OR "adapt*" OR "change*" OR "debug*" OR "refactor*" OR "comprehension" OR "test*" OR "analysis" OR "cognitive")
ACM Digital Library	("software visual*") AND ("maintenance" OR "evolution" OR "fault" OR "defect" OR "enhancement" OR "adapt*" OR "change*" OR "debug*" OR "refactor*" OR "comprehension" OR "test*" OR "analysis" OR "cognitive")
Science Direct	("software visual*") AND ("maintenance" OR "evolution" OR "fault" OR "defect" OR "enhancement" OR "adapt*" OR "change*" OR "debug*" OR "refactor*" OR "comprehension" OR "test*" OR "analysis" OR "cognitive")
SpringerLink	("software visual*") AND ("maintenance" OR "evolution" OR "fault" OR "defect" OR "enhancement" OR "adapt*" OR "change*" OR "debug*" OR "refactor*" OR "comprehension" OR "test*" OR "analysis" OR "cognitive")
Wiley Online Library	("software visual*") AND ("maintenance" OR "evolution" OR "fault" OR "defect" OR "enhancement" OR "adapt*" OR "change*" OR "debug*" OR "refactor*" OR "comprehension" OR "test*" OR "analysis" OR "cognitive")

TABLE A4
RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MAINTENANCE TASKS AND EVALUATION TYPES

Maintenance Task	Evaluation Types	Example Studies
Comprehension	Case Study, Application Example, Field Experiment, Human Subject Lab Experiment (LEHS), Software System Lab Experiment (LESS), Discussion, Experience Report, No Evaluation	S01, S02, S03, S04, S07, S10, S11, S13, S14, S15, S16, S17, S20, S21, S22, S23, S24, S26, S27, S29, S30, S31, S32, S33, S37, S46, S47, S49, S51, S52, S53, S54, S56, S57, S58, S60
Debugging	Case Study, Application Example, Field Experiment, LEHS, LESS, Experience Report, Simulation, No Evaluation	S01, S02, S03, S04, S06, S07, S09, S16, S17, S20, S22, S25, S26, S28, S29, S31, S37, S42, S44, S46, S50, S51, S55, S57, S61
Unspecified Maintenance Task	Case Study, Application Example, LEHS, Discussion, Experience Report, No Evaluation	S13, S15, S23, S27, S35, S38, S39, S48, S50
Understanding Dependencies	Case Study, Application Example, LEHS, LESS	S16, S18, S24, S39, S45, S58, S59
Refactoring	Case Study, Application Example, LEHS, LESS, Discussion	S02, S27, S40, S41, S53, S59
Code Analysis	Case Study, Experience Report	S43, S48, S49
Improve Code Quality	Application Example, LEHS, No Evaluation	S08, S09, S15
Code Review	Application Example, Field Experiment	S04, S19
Performance Optimization	Case Study, Application Example	S36, S44
Change Tracking	Application Example	S19, S40
Change Analysis	LEHS	S40
Boundary Detection	Case Study	S05
Dead Code Identification	Case Study	S01
Detect Interruptions	Case Study	S03
Explore Software Metrics	LEHS	S15
Malware Detection	Simulation, LESS	S34

TABLE A5
RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EVALUATION TYPES AND EMERGING TRENDS

Evaluation Type	Emerging Trends	Studies
Case Study	3D visualization, BVE technique, Blueprint, City metaphor, Dashboard, Heap patterns, Polymetric view, Scarf Plots, Treemaps, VR tool, Web	S05, S07, S08, S17, S23, S26, S27, S28, S33, S38, S42, S45, S46, S54, S60
Application Example	3D visualization, API, Bubble chart, City metaphor, Dashboard, Diagram, Metrics, Plugin, Timeline, Treemaps, VR tool, Web, Visualization	S06, S08, S09, S13, S15, S19, S21, S23, S27, S32, S33, S36, S37, S38, S40, S42, S43, S44, S50, S54, S55, S59, S61
Field Experiment	3D visualization, City metaphor, Web	S07, S09, S19, S23
LEHS (Lab Experiment Human Subjects)	3D visualization, Blueprint, Bubble chart, Dashboard, Diagram, Island metaphor, Minecraft, Plugin, Role-stereotypes, Timeline, Visualization, VR tool, Web	S06, S08, S13, S15, S17, S21, S31, S37, S38, S39, S42, S43, S44, S46, S47, S50, S52, S54, S55, S58
LESS (Lab Experiment Software System)	3D visualization, Call graphs, City metaphor, Dashboard, Heap patterns, Island metaphor, VR tool	S22, S23, S25, S27, S28, S33, S34, S38, S45, S46, S52, S54, S57
Simulation	Call graphs, Malware detection	S25, S34
Experience Report	Dashboard, Web, Visualization	S15, S43, S44, S50
Discussion	Blueprint, City metaphor, Minecraft, VR tool	S08, S17, S23, S45
No Evaluation	Code-map metaphor, Metrics, Node, Polymetric view, Role-stereotypes, Sequence diagram, UML Diagram, Visualization	S04, S09, S10, S13, S17, S21, S31, S39, S48, S51, S53, S58

TABLE A6
RELATION BETWEEN SOFTWARE MAINTENANCE TASKS, EMERGING TRENDS, AND RELATED STUDIES

Maintenance Task	Emerging Trends	Studies
Comprehension	3D visualization, VR tool, Dashboard, City metaphor, Node link diagram, Sequence diagram, Animation tool, Island metaphor, Treemaps, Web, Formula code, Metrics, Role-stereotypes, Node, Visualization, Blueprint, Polymetric view, Bubble chart, Elevated city, Scarf Plots, Timeline	S01, S02, S03, S04, S07, S10, S11, S13, S14, S15, S16, S17, S20, S21, S22, S23, S24, S26, S27, S29, S30, S31, S32, S33, S37, S46, S47, S49, S51, S52, S53, S54, S56, S57, S58, S60
Debugging	Call graphs, Heatmap, Dashboard, Animation tool, Plugin, Bubble chart, Tree graphs, Visualization, UML Diagram, Web	S01, S02, S03, S04, S06, S07, S09, S16, S17, S20, S22, S25, S26, S28, S29, S31, S37, S42, S44, S46, S50, S51, S55, S57, S61
Unspecified maintenance task	Dashboard, City metaphor, Web, VR tool, Plugin	S13, S15, S23, S27, S35, S38, S39, S48, S50
Understand dependencies	Node link diagram, VR tool, Web, API, Island metaphor, Node	S16, S18, S24, S39, S45, S58, S59
Refactoring	3D visualization, API, Plugin, Visualization, City metaphor, Web, Blueprint	S02, S27, S40, S41, S53, S59
Code analysis	Dashboard, Plugin, Web	S43, S48, S49
Improve code quality	3D visualization, Code-map metaphor, Web, Minecraft	S08, S09, S15
Code review	UML Diagram, Web	S04, S19
Performance optimization	Dashboard, Visualization, Web	S36, S44
Track changes	Dashboard, Plugin, Web	S19, S40
Analyze changes	Plugin	S40
Boundary detection	3D visualization, BVE technique	S05
Dead code identification	Call graphs	S01
Detect disruptions	Visualization	S03
Explore software metrics	Dashboard, Metrics	S15
Malware detection	Call graphs	S34